

Viscometric investigations and molecular interactions of triphenodioxazine dyes in mixed organic solvents

K. G. Ojha^a, L. C. Heda^b, C. Pareek^b and S. R. Mosalpur^{b*}

^aDepartment of Pure and Applied Chemistry, M. D. S. University, Ajmer-305 009, Rajasthan, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, S. D. Govt. College, Beawar-305 901, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : la157heda@yahoo.com, msonraj@yahoo.com, pareekcd@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 5 March 2008, revised 31 December 2008, accepted 1 January 2009

Abstract : Colloid chemical behaviour of 6,13-dichloro-3,10-dimethyl triphenodioxazine (TPDO-I) and 6,13-dibromo-3,10-dimethyl triphenodioxazine (TPDO-II) in non-aqueous solvent mixture benzene-methanol of varying composition has been investigated by viscometric measurements at 303 ± 0.1 K. The viscosity of the system increases with the increase in triphenodioxazine concentration. The Trend Change Point (TCP) values have been determined by intersection of two straight lines which are found to be dependent on the composition of solvent mixtures. The study confirms that the nature of triphenodioxazine agglomerate formed below and above 50% benzene concentration is quite different. The viscometric data have been analysed in terms of Einstein, Vand, Moulik and Jones-Dole equations. These well known equations have been successfully applied to explain the results of viscosity measurements and the viscometric parameters show that the behaviour of triphenodioxazine dyes changes in the proximity of 50% benzene concentration.

Keywords : Triphenodioxazine dye, trend change point, dye aggregation, viscosity, solute-solute interaction, solute-solvent interaction.

Introduction

The most striking feature of triphenodioxazine dyes of phenoxazine series has been their increasing importance in industrial and other allied applications because of influential effect of aggregation on dyeing processes¹⁻⁴. These are significantly useful for colouring plastics, varnishes, viscose, lacquers, paper and rubber in different shades due to stability and low solubility in common organic solvent^{5,6}. Some of the derivatives possess pharmacological properties like analgesic, anti-spasmodic and tranquilising effect⁷⁻⁹. In view of the potential application of these compounds, the present work has been undertaken to explain colloid chemical behaviour in mixed solvents. Benzene and methanol have been chosen as the co-solvents in the title study, since triphenodioxazines possess not only low solubility in pure organic solvent but also in mixed solvents. However, mixed solvents have a tendency to interact with triphenodioxazine molecules which affect the aggregation of molecules. The aggregation phenomenon has been widely studied giving different results and variance over several years^{10,11}. The viscosity data based on various equations has been exten-

sively used to furnish information concerning the structural changes in solution, trend change point (TCP) and nature of triphenodioxazine-solvent interaction. These vital informations play an important role in their selection for various industrial and biological applications.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. A number of substituted 1,4-benzoxazino-[2,3-*b*]phenoxazines (triphenodioxazines) were synthesised by the method reported earlier which involves condensation of substituted anilines with halogeno-*p*-benzoquinone in ethanolic solution in the presence of fused sodium acetate followed by oxidative cyclisation of resulting dianilino-*p*-benzoquinone with benzoyl chloride in nitrobenzene¹². The purity of compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silica gel G using various non-aqueous solvent systems. The solubility of triphenodioxazines in benzene and methanol was determined by preparing a saturated solution of triphenodioxazine in the solvent. The clear supernatant liquid was taken out (when the equilibrium was attained at the desired temperature) and analysed by weigh-

ing. The viscosity of triphenodioxazine solutions were measured by Ostwald's viscometer in a thermostated bath. The viscometer was calibrated frequently with distilled water. The viscosity results were checked against viscosity of known solutions and accuracy was found to be nearly 0.3%. Precautions regarding prevention of evaporation of solvent were taken in all the cases.

Results and discussion

The flow of characterisation of triphenodioxazine solutions in terms of viscometric measurements has been employed as a tool to find out the TCP of the triphenodioxazine dyes in benzene-methanol mixtures. The viscosity of TPDO in solutions of varying composition of benzene-methanol mixtures increases with the increase in the dye concentration (Table 1). The increase in viscosity with the increase in triphenodioxazine concentration may be due to the increasing tendency of triphenodioxazine

causes the formation of triphenodioxazine aggregates. It is apparent from the data that the values of TCP are dependent on the composition of solvent mixtures. The values of TCP in the solution containing benzene below 50% are lower as compared to those containing higher volume percent of benzene (Table 2). The order of TCP is as follows :

$$\text{TCP (below 50\% benzene)} < \text{TCP (above 50\% benzene)}$$

This may be attributed to the change in the mobility of the triphenodioxazine molecules due to change in the dielectric constant of the solvent mixture having different composition of benzene-methanol. Further it is suggested that predominance of lipophilic character in the solvent mixture plays a pertinent role in the clustering alignment of the solute molecules. Thus there is delay in the aggregation due to increase in the interaction between lipophilic solvent and solute molecules. The viscosity data reveals that the TCP of TPDO-I and TPDO-II tripheno-

Table 1. Viscosity, η , of TPDO-I and TPDO-II in benzene-methanol at 303 ± 0.1 K in millipoise

Concn. (mol dm ⁻³)	Volume percent of benzene in solvent mixture					
	25		50		75	
	TPDO-I	TPDO-II	TPDO-I	TPDO-II	TPDO-I	TPDO-II
0.001	5.2994	5.3004	5.4551	5.4706	5.6098	5.5944
0.003	5.3168	5.4062	5.4959	5.5833	5.6864	5.6884
0.005	5.3565	5.5168	5.5374	5.6805	5.7704	5.7711
0.007	5.3906	5.6234	5.5802	5.7848	5.8661	5.8654
0.009	5.4484	5.7012	5.6095	5.8702	5.9504	5.9490
0.010	5.4863	5.7447	5.6343	5.9123	5.9725	5.9771
0.012	5.5611	5.8116	5.6727	5.9732	6.0169	6.0155
0.014	5.6327	5.9144	5.7031	6.0265	6.0567	6.0511

molecules to associate in the form of clustering entity in the triphenodioxazine-solvent system. The molecular interaction, molecular association in colloidal solution and the number of characterising aspects of physico-chemical behaviour of binary liquid mixtures and mixed solvent have been reported by the number of workers¹³⁻¹⁷. The difference in the viscosities of triphenodioxazine solutions in varying composition of benzene-methanol mixtures is mainly due to the difference in the viscosities of the solvent mixtures. The plots of viscosity (η) against triphenodioxazine concentration (C) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite dye concentration corresponding to TCP of the triphenodioxazine (Fig. 1). Of course this is the maximum concentration of molecular dispersion where balancing of the internal forces

dioxazines follow the order :

$$\text{TPDO-II} > \text{TPDO-I.}$$

The viscosity of triphenodioxazine solutions as well as those of the solvent mixtures increase as the volume percent of benzene increases which may be attributed to the cumulative effect of the variation of dielectric constant, degree of aggregation and the nature of the triphenodioxazine agglomerate.

The values of specific viscosity (η_{sp}) of TPDO-I and TPDO-II solutions in varying compositions of benzene-methanol mixtures also increase with the increase in the dye concentration. The nature of curves and TCP values are in good agreement with those observed for viscosity data. The fluidity of TPDO solutions in benzene-methanol mixtures decreases with the increase in the TPDO

Fig. 1. Plots of η versus C for triphenodioxazine (TPDO) in benzene-methanol. Plots : TPDO; (○) TPDO-I, (□) TPDO-II.

concentration as well as with the increase in volume percent of benzene. A perusal of Table 2 indicates that TCP values are in good agreement with those derived from viscosity and specific viscosity curves and are dependent on the solvent composition i.e. TCP order of η , η_{sp} and ϕ are TPDO-II > TPDO-I for all varying compositions of benzene-methanol mixtures.

Einstein and Vand equations :

The viscosity results have been explained in terms of equations proposed by Einstein¹⁸ and Vand¹⁹.

$$\text{Einstein : } \eta_{sp} = 2.5 \bar{V} C$$

$$\text{Vand : } \frac{1}{C} = \left[\frac{0.921}{\bar{V}} \right]^{-1} \frac{1}{\log (\eta / \eta_0)} + Q \bar{V}$$

where \bar{V} , C , Q , η , η_0 and η_{sp} are molar volume, concentration, interaction coefficient, viscosity of the solution, viscosity of solvent and specific viscosity respectively. The plots of specific viscosity (η_{sp}) against triphenodioxazine concentration (C) are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite concentration which corresponds to the TCP of the dye. The plots with intercept almost equal to zero are linear below TCP, which shows that the equation proposed by Einstein is applicable to dilute solutions of triphenodioxazine²⁰. It is observed that the values of molar volume \bar{V} (Table 3) obtained from the plots of Einstein equation and Vand equation below TCP increase gradually up to 50% benzene and then increase rapidly beyond 50% benzene. Whereas above TCP, molar volume decreases rapidly up to 50%

Table 2. Values of TCP (mol dm⁻³)

Triphenodioxazine	Plots	Volume percent of benzene in solvent mixture		
		25	50	75
TPDO-I	η vs C	0.0075	0.0080	0.0090
	η_{sp} vs C	0.0077	0.0082	0.0090
	ϕ vs C	0.0075	0.0081	0.0091
TPDO-II	ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C}	0.0076	0.0080	0.0090
	η vs C	0.0070	0.0082	0.0092
	η_{sp} vs C	0.0072	0.0084	0.0093
	ϕ vs C	0.0071	0.0083	0.0092
	ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C}	0.0070	0.0085	0.0090

Table 3. Values of molar volume (\bar{V}) of TPDO-I and TPDO-II in benzene-methanol derived from Einstein and Vand equations

Triphenodioxazine	Percent of benzene	Einstein equation		Vand equation	
		\bar{V}_1	\bar{V}_2	\bar{V}_1	\bar{V}_2
TPDO-I	25	1.11	2.80	1.00	1.38
	50	1.45	1.69	1.05	1.19
	75	3.07	1.53	4.42	2.79
TPDO-II	25	3.33	3.20	4.01	3.38
	50	3.50	2.26	4.05	2.94
	75	4.00	1.33	5.89	2.81

benzene and then decreases gradually beyond 50% benzene. It may be attributed to the fact that the entrapping of solvent molecules in the palisade layers of triphenodioxazine clustering below 50% benzene is dissimilar to the entrapping of solvent above this concentration. It is interesting to note that the values of molar volume enumerated from these equations are almost equal and the trend remains unaltered irrespective of the type of equation applied.

Moulik's equation :

The Moulik equation²¹ also fits well to the triphenodioxazine solutions as the plots $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 are almost linear.

$$\left[\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} \right]^2 = M + KC^2$$

where M and K are constants.

The values of M and K have been calculated from the intercepts and slopes of the $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs C^2 plots (Fig. 2) and are recorded in Table 4. It has been found that the values of M are almost equal up to 50% benzene and above this concentration of benzene, the pattern shows increase in values of M . The values of M follow the order :

$$M_2 \text{ (above TCP)} > M_1 \text{ (below TCP)}$$

A perusal of Table 4 reveals that the value of K decreases rapidly upto 50% benzene and then decreases gradually. This implies that a change of behaviour occurs in the periphery of 50% benzene concentration and the nature of solvent plays a pertinent role in ordering and compacting the scattered clustering units.

Unlike M , the stipulated values of K follow the order :

$$K_1 \text{ (below TCP)} > K_2 \text{ (above TCP)}$$

Jones-Dole equation :

The viscosity data have also been interpreted in the light of Jones-Dole equation²².

$$\frac{(\eta/\eta_0 - 1)}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C}$$

For convenience, the equation may be expressed as

$$\frac{\psi}{\sqrt{C}} = A + B\sqrt{C}$$

where the coefficients A and B refer to solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions respectively. The plots ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} (Fig. 3) for both the triphenodioxazines studied here were found to be linear with least scatter. These plots are characterised by two straight lines intersecting

Fig. 2. Plots of $[\eta/\eta_0]^2$ versus C^2 for triphenodioxazine (TPDO) in benzene-methanol. Plots : TPDO; (○) TPDO-I, (◻) TPDO-II.

Table 4. Viscosity parameters of TPDO in benzene-methanol derived from different equations

Triphenodioxazine	Volume (%) of benzene	Moulik's equation				Jones-Dole equation			
		M_1	M_2	K_1	K_2	A_1	A_2	B_1	B_2
TPDO-I	25	1.02	1.05	0.8812	0.3838	0.045	-0.230	3.735	9.166
	50	1.02	1.07	0.8097	0.3057	0.050	0.151	4.791	2.727
	75	1.06	1.13	0.7320	0.2248	0.250	0.617	7.556	1.739
TPDO-II	25	1.07	1.12	1.6003	0.5543	0.182	0.530	9.230	5.555
	50	1.07	1.11	1.3763	0.4663	0.210	0.600	10.000	6.250
	70	1.08	1.15	1.1917	0.2216	0.150	0.640	11.666	1.666

at a point corresponding to the TCP of triphenodioxazines. The values of TCP are in good agreement with the values derived from the plots of η , η_{sp} and ϕ vs C (Table 2). In view of the two intersecting straight lines for ψ/\sqrt{C} vs \sqrt{C} plots, it is logical to evaluate two values of both the coefficients below and above TCP designated as A_1 , B_1 and A_2 , B_2 respectively (Table 4). It is observed that the values of these constants depend on the composition of the solvent mixtures.

It is evident from the Table 4 that although the values of constant A are positive but are of small magnitude for

both the triphenodioxazines in the entire composition range of benzene-methanol mixture thereby showing the presence of very weak solute-solute interactions. In other words, both the triphenodioxazines studied here, mix ideally with benzene-methanol mixture and there is a perfect solvation of these molecules resulting in weak solute-solute interactions²³. Also, the values of constant A are smaller than the values of constant B , which confirms that triphenodioxazine molecules do not aggregate appreciably below TCP while there is sudden change in the aggregation above TCP.

Fig. 3. Plots of ψ/\sqrt{C} versus \sqrt{C} for triphenodioxazine (TPDO) in benzene-methanol. Plots : TPDO; (○) TPDO-I, (□) TPDO-II.

It is observed that the values of constant B , for both the triphenodioxazines in various composition of solvent are fairly large thereby suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. The values of constant B also increase with the increasing concentration of benzene in the solvent mixtures, thereby indicating that solute-solvent interactions increase with the increase of concentration of benzene in the solvent mixtures²³. A perusal of Table 4 shows that there is large difference in the positive values of B_1 and B_2 , which is in conformity with the observation that B is always positive in non-aqueous media²⁴. It is observed that the values of constants A and B increase slowly up to 50% benzene and then increase rapidly therefore it is not contrary to the concept of Hartley²⁵. This concept pre-supposes that clustering entities are highly dynamic and flexible. Frank and Evans²⁶ and Latimer²⁷ showed that the change in behaviour of macromolecules is due to the change in degree of clustering of macromolecules possessing micellar characteristics. The tendency of periodic character of triphenodioxazine clustering is less pronounced below 50% benzene due to predominance of alcohol yielding low values of solute-solvent interactions. It is interesting to point out that the values of constant B are greater in the predominance of benzene in the solvent mixture. This may be due to the fact that the agglomeration of triphenodioxazine molecules beyond TCP boosts up the electro-kinetic forces,

causing more intake of the solvent in the voids left in the cluster packing, resulting in increasing viscosity and hence increasing values of constant B . The trend of coefficients may thus be summed up as

$$A_2 > A_1, B_1 > B_2$$

Summary :

It has been observed that the viscosity of the system increases with the increase in TPDO concentration. The increasing trend of viscosity may be due to combined effect of the variation of dielectric constant of solvent, degree of aggregation and nature of the dye agglomerate. The TCP values obtained from different viscosity data are in good agreement and show maximum concentration of molecular dispersion at which aggregation of dye initiates.

It has been confirmed repeatedly using various viscometric parameters that the nature of dye agglomerate formed below and above 50% benzene concentration is dissimilar. Further, this has been supported by group additivity concept which clearly intimates that the change in molecular structure i.e. substitution by chloro, bromo, methyl etc. changes the molecular interactions^{28,29}. It is because of change in behaviour of TPDO dyes in the proximity of 50% benzene concentration. It has been inferred that behaviour of triphenodioxazine dyes in benzene dominated and methanol dominated solvents is quite

different as these co-solvents occupy different positions in the palisade layers of dye aggregates.

It is noteworthy to point out on the basis of results obtained that the above treatment gives a phenomenological description of clustering profile and confirms the existence of triphenodioxazine aggregation in the non-aqueous mixed solvent.

References

1. T. Hihara, Y. Okada and Z. Morita, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2000, **45**, 131.
2. B. C. Burdett, "Aggregation of Dyes", 'Aggregation Processes in Solution, Studies in Physical and Theoretical Chemistry', Vol. 26, eds. E. Wyn-Jones and J. Gormally, Elsevier, 1983, **10**, p. 241.
3. T. Hihara, Y. Okada and Z. Morita, *Dyes and Pigments*, 2000, **46**, 181.
4. (a) K. Venkataraman (ed.), "The Chemistry of Synthetic Dyes", Academic Press, New York, Vol. 2, Chap. XXV, p. 761; (b) H. Jaeger, European Pat. Appl. 1991, DE 4, 101, 067 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1993, **188**, 104785).
5. CIBA Ltd., US Pat., 1956, 2, 763, 641 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1957, **51**, 3153b).
6. R. C. Harris and G. C. Newland, British Pat., 1966, 1, 034, 181 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, **65**, 9115b).
7. A. Krantz, R. W. Spancer, T. F. Tam, T. J. Liak, L. J. Copp, E. M. Thomes and S. D. Rafferty, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1990, **33**, 464.
8. G. Kumaran and G. H. Kulkarni, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, **33**, 877.
9. B. Hajjem, A. Chini and B. Baccar, *Synth. Commun.*, 1992, **22**, 295.
10. R. H. Peters, "Aggregation of Dyes in Solution. Textile Chemistry", Vol. III, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1975, Chap. 27, p. 851.
11. E. Coates, *Journal of the Society of Dyers and Colourists*, 1969, **85**, 355.
12. S. K. Jain, K. G. Ojha and R. R. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **17**, 278.
13. H. Suzuki, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **47**, 273.
14. W. Scholtan, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1955, **142**, 84.
15. W. Scholtan, *Med. Chem. Abhandl. Med. Chem. Forschungsstatten Forbenfabriken Bayer*, 1956, **5**, 295.
16. R. P. Verma, K. Singh and H. Singh, *Annali di Chimica*, 1978, **68**, 415.
17. V. P. Mehta, M. Hasan and L. C. Heda, *Afinidad*, 1982, **39**, 385.
18. A. Einstein, *Annalen der Physik.*, 1906, **19**, 289; 1911, **34**, 591.
19. V. Vand, *J. Physical Colloid Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277.
20. K. N. Mehrotra, K. Tandon and M. K. Rawat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **69**, 719.
21. S. P. Moulik, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4682.
22. G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
23. M. L. Parmar, D. K. Dhiman and R. C. Thakur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 2032.
24. R. Gopal and P. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 368.
25. G. S. Hartley, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1938, **34**, 1288.
26. H. S. Frank and M. W. Evans, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.
27. W. M. Latimer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1936, **18**, 349.
28. L. Lepori and P. Gianni, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2000, **29**, 405.
29. P. Gianni and L. Lepori, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1996, **25**, 1.